

A Competitive Analysis on Resources Allocation for the Platformization of Manufacturing

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Abstract

Manufacturing is once again at a turning point. Influenced by recent global economic and political developments, as well as technological advancements, the industry is experiencing significant shifts. Public cloud manufacturing is emerging as a new model that integrates the capabilities of small and medium-sized manufacturers and connects them with consumers, functioning as a unique and complex platform for facilitating a bilateral market. With the growing demand for flexibility and cost-effectiveness in resource allocation, these platforms play a critical role in efficiently matching customers with manufacturers, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency, robustness, and resilience for supply chain disruptions of the manufacturing system. In recent years, considerable attention has been given to the challenges of resource allocation within these platforms. However, a comprehensive analysis of decentralized approaches that consider bilateral interests is still lacking and the concept of platform-based resources distribution tailored to small and medium-sized manufacturing companies in the EU remains largely unexplored. This paper provides a detailed survey of recent research findings, with the objective of discussing current solutions, proposing the classification of methodologies and identifying challenges in the allocation of resources on public cloud platforms. Additionally, it outlines a vision for a new manufacturing paradigm, addressing the evolving manufacturing landscape and suggesting directions for future research.

Keywords: Cloud Manufacturing, Resource Allocation, Matching Theory, Auction Theory

1. Introduction

Manufacturing serves as the backbone of national economies, with small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) playing a crucial role in this industry [1]. According to the Annual Report on European SMES of 2022/2023, SMEs accounted for 52.3% of total employment in the European manufacturing sector, with 99.3% of all companies classified as SMEs, and 84.4% of these being categorized as micro-SMEs, employing fewer than 10 people [2].

European manufacturing SMEs are recognized for their extensive industry experience [3]; however, such a lean manufacturing model has faced various challenges in recent years. Their small size often makes them vulnerable to supply chain disruptions [4]. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the global supply chain was severely disrupted, sparking discussions about maintaining local production capacity to enhance the resilience of regional manufacturing systems against future unforeseen events [5].

Additionally, with the growing demand for product customization [6], a key aspect of Industry 5.0—which focuses on the interaction between manufacturing and society, as well as the adaptability of factories—the need for more flexible suppliers has grown significantly. In an era characterized by fluctuating market demands and fragile supply chains, a recent EU report highlights that SMEs are experiencing slower productivity growth compared to larger companies [7], with capacity utilization rates that are also lower [8]. Moreover, their limited scale hampers their ability to compete for large-volume orders [9].

Against this backdrop, SMEs have several key objectives: enhancing their competitiveness in large-scale customization projects [10], improving capacity utilization, and mitigating supply chain risks [4]. On the consumer side, there is increasing demand for cost-effective solutions, shorter lead times, and greater flexibility [11]. European manufacturing was once regarded as a global leader, and the challenges it faces today reflect those seen across the global manufacturing sector. This highlights the urgent need for a new manufacturing paradigm that strengthens and unifies the capacity, flexibility, and resilience of regional manufacturing systems.

The demands from both sides of the manufacturing market have driven the emergence of two-sided platforms that connect manufacturing suppliers with customers [12], which have become a key paradigm for capitalizing on the strengths of European manufacturing SMEs. The rise of cloud manufacturing (CMfg) has provided the technological foundation for these plat-

forms [13]. Two-sided platforms in the manufacturing market capitalize on the concept of decentralized manufacturing, leveraging the strengths of small and medium-sized companies while providing customers with cost-effective, flexible and high-quality solutions. In recent years, significant attention from both academia and industry has focused on developing CMfg platforms to coordinate interactions between customers and numerous manufacturers, positioning them as a solution to the challenges faced by SMEs [14].

Matching the right manufacturer with customer orders, as identified as Manufacturing Resource Allocation, is a core function of CMfg[15]. Acting as a coordinator between customers and manufacturers, CMfg leverages Manufacturing Resource Matching to optimize benefits for both parties [16]. In general, the Manufacturing Resource Allocation focuses on aligning the most suitable manufacturing resource providers (manufacturers) with resource demanders (customers) within the manufacturing system [17] [18]. However, different products and supply chains require consideration of specific characteristics. For instance, in the 3D printing market, manufacturers seek to utilize unused capacity through cloud manufacturing platforms without disrupting their existing distribution channels [19].

As a mechanism designer, the platform must balance the interests of both sides, but the complexity of the manufacturing system makes this far more challenging than a typical mechanism design problem. While some valuable overview articles exist, they primarily focus on private CMfg platforms [20]. Therefore, a comprehensive and thorough research analysis is urgently needed to organize and summarize the development and gaps in matching algorithms for cloud manufacturing platforms.

This paper is part of the EU-funded research project MARS¹, which seeks to develop a distributed cloud manufacturing platform to integrate and coordinate the capacities of small and medium-sized European manufacturing enterprises. The manufacturing resource allocation is one of the most essential components of the MARS platform. This paper aims to discuss the development of manufacturing resource allocation, propose a categorized summary of current methodologies, and identify existing gaps to guide future research. Building on this paper, a series of system design initiatives for MARS will be proposed in subsequent work.

¹Manufacturing Architecture for Resilience and Sustainability (MARS), <https://mars-horizon.eu/>

Several key research questions are addressed in this paper:

1. What are the definitions of the CMfg platform and the Manufacturing Resource Allocation problem?
2. How can allocation problems be categorized?
3. What are the current state-of-the-art approaches for solving the allocation problem?
4. What are the existing research gaps, and what are the future directions for this field?

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the definition of the manufacturing resource allocation problem; Section 3 presents the classification and overview of mechanisms; Section 4 discusses criteria for evaluating allocation results; Section 5 reviews the state-of-the-art solutions; Section 6 discusses the current gap and future research directions; and finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. From Decentralized to Cloud manufacturing

2.1. Decentralized Manufacturing

Since the early twentieth century, large-scale, centralized manufacturing has been the dominant model in industries, with Ford's assembly line serving as a landmark event [21]. Manufacturers typically established production lines in a fixed location, as centralized mass production, according to the theory of economies of scale, allowed for significant cost reductions by producing in large quantities [22]. By the end of the 20th century, decentralized manufacturing gained significant attention, driven by several key factors [23]:

1. **Rising Transportation Costs and Risks:** In centralized production, factors such as tariffs, unforeseen events, and environmental concerns have increased transportation costs for manufacturers. [24]
2. **Affiliated Operations in Complex Manufacturing Processes:** The modular development of products and the complexity of manufacturing processes have made joint manufacturing by multiple manufacturers in decentralized environments a practical solution. [25]
3. **Reduced Inventory and Flexible Manufacturing:** A typical example is Just-in-Time (JIT) manufacturing, widely favored by Japanese companies. This approach reduces inventory by producing on demand, often resulting in production activities being located closer to customers. [26].

In the 21st century, distributed manufacturing has received increased attention, supported by the continuous advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The Internet of Things (IoT) facilitates the management of production processes by platforms and manufacturers [27], while blockchain technology ensures product quality assurance [28]. Additionally, cloud computing enables the execution of large-scale computational tasks in the cloud [29].

The concept of cloud manufacturing (CMfg) has emerged with the support of cloud computing, IoT, artificial intelligence, and other advanced technologies [30] [31], and it has also become a practical model for distributed manufacturing in the modern era [32].

2.2. Cloud Manufacturing

Figure 1: Geographically distributed cloud manufacturing

Cloud manufacturing (CMfg) was first proposed by Li Bo in 2010 [33], introducing a new paradigm for a high-tech, networked, and intelligent manufacturing system [30]. Since its introduction, the concept of CMfg has

garnered significant attention from both academia and industry. Over the following years, practical models and definitions of CMfg have been further expanded [34]. Figure 1 illustrates how CMfg connects customers with geographically distributed manufacturers through the cloud.

In the years following its introduction, the practical model of cloud manufacturing has been further expanded, with researchers categorizing it into Private Cloud Manufacturing, Public Cloud Manufacturing, Community Cloud Manufacturing, and Hybrid Cloud Manufacturing [35]. In a private cloud, a company typically coordinates its own distributed production across multiple machines or factories using cloud manufacturing [36]. In community clouds, several companies collaborate to participate in joint manufacturing tasks [37]. Public clouds involve a bilateral platform that connects resource demanders and providers, where the platform acts as an intermediary, orchestrating the complex interactions between these parties [38]. Hybrid clouds combine private and public cloud scheduling, requiring a comprehensive approach to resource matching and scheduling [35].

In private cloud manufacturing, machines or factories are geographically distributed, but decision-making remains centralized [39]. On the other hand, the public cloud manufacturing platform operates as a multi-agent system, where each participant—both customers and manufacturers—acts as an autonomous decision-maker responsible for data, pricing, and local production. The platform's role is to optimize the overall system's efficiency by designing effective mechanisms [32]. Community cloud manufacturing is a specialized form of public cloud manufacturing, but it retains a centralized decision-making structure.

The primary focus of this paper is on manufacturing resource matching and task allocation within public cloud platforms. Public cloud manufacturing has provided significant benefits to SMEs, allowing them to sell excess capacity through the platform, while consumers gain access to more cost-effective solutions.

2.3. Main Components

There are three main participants in decentralized cloud manufacturing: the Resource Demander, the Platform, and the Resource Provider [40], as illustrated in Figure 1.

The Resource Demander, also referred to as customers or consumers in the context of some literature, represents individuals or organizations in need of manufacturing resources who place orders. Typically, they provide specific

requirements for the part to the platform, or they may already have design files (e.g., Computer-Aided Design files). Their primary criteria are quality, lead time, and price [41].

The platform acts as a coordinator between demanders and providers, with the primary goal of designing a matching mechanism that connects the system's components and ensures they work together to maximize overall benefits. To achieve this, it integrates various functionalities, such as quality control and blockchain-based quality assurance [42].

The Resource Provider, also referred to as manufacturers in the context of some literature, represents organizations with available manufacturing capacity and capabilities. These providers possess physical equipment, such as machine tools, as well as the expertise and knowledge required for manufacturing [43].

Resource Demanders and Providers form a multi-agent system that collaborates and communicates with each other, and the next section describes the problem definition of how to design a mechanism to connect the two sides of the market.

2.4. Problem Definition

Assuming that in the manufacturing market, the resource demanders set is $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{|D|}\}$ in total. The resource providers set is $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$.

Several basic assumptions underpin the market:

1. **Autonomy:** All participants, both customers and manufacturers, have the freedom to decide whether to join the platform, share data, participate in orders, and engage in other activities [44].
2. **Geographical Dispersion:** Participants are geographically dispersed, with manufacturers responsible solely for production, while the platform manages logistics, quality control, and other related functions [23].
3. **External Competitiveness:** Customers may also source capacity from platforms in the market or big manufacturers [45].

The three main components in the market—resource demanders, resource providers, and platforms—each have distinct interests and areas of focus. [46]. Customers seek to obtain the highest quality products within the shortest possible time and at the lowest cost [47]. For resource providers, the primary concern is profitability, and they are motivated to participate in public cloud manufacturing platforms for several reasons:

1. Engagement in mass and complex orders: Large-scale equipment manufacturing is often too complex for a single manufacturer to handle. The distributed manufacturing model enables companies on the platform to collaborate on such projects [48]. From the customer's perspective, manufacturers on cloud platforms are decentralized yet perceived as sufficiently productive communities.
2. Sale of surplus capacity: Manufacturers with unused capacity can sell this surplus at a slightly lower price without affecting their original sales channels [49].

In this market, the platform's role is to design a mechanism that facilitates the matching process in a way that benefits both parties [38]. However, there is often a conflict of interests between resource demanders and resource providers, requiring platforms to find an appropriate trade-off through matching and negotiation strategies [50].

The expected outcome of the mechanism is to develop a smart and robust distribution that allocates manufacturing resources to the demand side in order to meet specific objectives. In some cases, such as additive manufacturing, a single resource provider's capacity can satisfy the needs of at least one resource demander [51]. However, in large-scale equipment manufacturing, fulfilling a single order often requires the combined capacity of multiple resource providers [52].

To avoid ambiguity, the task set $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{|T|}\}$ is used to denote the sum of all manufacturing tasks and it is assumed that each resource provider can undertake at least one task. The allocation scheme is represented by the mapping function $f : T \rightarrow D$. There may be multiple objectives for mapping f that need to be maximized (minimized), such as benefits for each participant, or energy consumption. Let the set of objective functions associated with f for all objectives be: $O(f) = \{o_1(f), o_2(f), \dots, o_{|O|}(f)\}$ [53]. The task of the mechanism designer is to find f that can satisfy: $\max O(f)$.

In this section, the three participating entities in the public cloud manufacturing platform and the definitions of their interests and matching problems are presented. The specific allocation processes and algorithms are discussed in the next section.

3. Classification of Task Allocation Approaches

3.1. Introduction to Task Allocation Frameworks

Figure 2 presents a classification of frameworks and algorithms for task assignment on public cloud manufacturing platforms. Overall, three different frameworks have been applied to this domain: one-sided matching, two-sided matching, and auction-based methods.

Figure 2: Classification of the allocation methods

Generally, matching methods involve the process of forming an optimal mapping between manufacturers and customers to maximize total profit [54]. One-sided matching focuses on the interests or preferences of a single party, allowing the platform to generate a distribution that optimizes outcomes for that side [55]. In contrast, two-sided matching incorporates the preference information of both parties involved [56]. Its goal is to establish a stable match that aligns with the preferences of both sides, ensuring mutual satisfaction with the allocation of manufacturing services or orders [57]. The auction-based approach determines the allocation of manufacturing resources by ranking bids. The platform sets an auction target or defines a bidding method to balance the interests of both manufacturers and customers [58].

Due to the decentralized nature of CMfg, platform allocations are based on incomplete information. The three allocation methods discussed above represent mechanism designs tailored to decision-making under incomplete

information, each addressing different scenarios and objectives. These frameworks are further categorized and examined in detail in the following subsections.

3.2. One-sided Matching

One-sided matching refers to a process in which only the attributes and interest of one side are considered during the matching process. This approach is commonly used in industrial platform services [59], such as 3DHubs [60]. The main advantage of one-sided matching is its speed, as the platform can quickly generate solutions using mathematical models [61] or heuristic methods [62], allowing customers to receive instant quotes. However, the drawback is that the focus on only one side of the process may cause participants on the other side to leave the platform. Figure 3 illustrates the one-sided matching approach.

Figure 3: One-sided Matching

The platform operates with two pools: one storing customer information and the other storing manufacturer information. Based on the data from both pools, the platform generates the matching.

A typical one-sided approach is as follows:

1. Information Upload: Customers upload order information and manufacturers upload resources information to the platform,
2. Task Composition: The platform breaks down orders uploaded by customers,

3. Matching: The decomposed manufacturing tasks are matched with the manufacturers' production capacity,
4. Return Proposal: Returns the matching result to both sides for their confirmation.

3.3. Two-sided Matching

Matching algorithms are typically categorized into one-to-one [63], more-to-one [64], and many-to-many matches [65]. For example, marriage matching represents a one-to-one match, while organ donation is a many-to-many match. However, in the context of public cloud platform algorithms, this categorization is not directly applicable, as the number of matching pairs depends on the capacity of the manufacturer. Figure 4 illustrates the two-sided matching approach.

Figure 4: Two-sided Matching

A typical two-sided approach is as follows:

1. Information Upload: Customers upload order details, while manufacturers provide resource information. The preference lists are provided after reviewing other side's attributes,
2. Task Composition: The platform breaks down orders uploaded by customers,
3. Matching: The stable matching are generated based on their preference,

4. Return Proposal: Returns the matching result to both parties.

Two-sided matching is an algorithm that considers the preferences and attributes of both the customer and manufacturer sides [66]. The allocation process takes into account the interests of both parties, and is often modeled using game-theoretic principles. Depending on the preference information, two-sided matching can be further classified into probability preference-based matching, fuzzy preference-Based matching, hybrid preference-based matching, and historical information-based matching:

- Probability Preference-Based Matching: Each attribute provided by manufacturers and customers is modeled using a probability distribution function [67]. This information is then integrated with a utility equation to quantify preferences and generate a preference ranking.
- Fuzzy Preference-Based Matching: In scenarios where participants provide unclear or hesitant preference rankings, this approach effectively manages ambiguous preference information, ensuring more accurate and flexible matching outcomes [68].
- Hybrid Preference-Based Matching: This approach seeks to combine the advantages of both Probability and Fuzzy methods, integrating the strengths of each to enhance the matching process.
- Historical Information-Based Matching: This method uses data from previous transactions to predict new preferences, allowing for more informed matching decisions [69].

Preference-based two-sided matching facilitates the generation of stable, mutually stable matches for the platform, while the auction-based method offers an alternative allocation approach suitable for competitive manufacturing resources scenarios.

3.4. Auction-based Method

Auctions are another common method of resource allocation, where participants bid on orders or manufacturing resources, and the platform serves as the mechanism designer, setting the bidding rules. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 5. Depending on which side acts as the bidder, the following auction methods can be categorized:

A typical auction-based approach is as follows (assume manufacturers are bidders):

Figure 5: Manufacturing Resource Auction

1. Customers upload order information information to the platform.
2. The platform breaks down orders uploaded by customers,
3. The platform invites manufacturers capable of producing these tasks to conduct auctions, and the winner of different tasks is determined based on their offers,
4. Returns the matching result to both parties.

3.4.1. Demander-as-bidders Auctions

In this type of auction, resource providers (manufacturers) submit details about their manufacturing resources, and resource demanders (customers) place bids to access them. This approach is commonly applied in additive manufacturing, where resource seekers, such as 3D designers, bid for resource time on equipment like 3D printers [19].

3.4.2. Provider-as-bidders Auctions

Manufacturers bid for manufacturing orders in this auction, with the winning manufacturer securing the order by offering a price lower than their competitors [70].

3.4.3. Double Auctions

Double Auctions involve simultaneous bidding by both manufacturers and customers for a certain order [71]. Manufacturers submit their offers, while customers specify the prices they are willing to pay. Typically, the manufacturer with the highest bid and the customer with the lowest bid are paired as the winners of the auction [72].

4. Evaluation Criteria for Allocation Schemes in CMfg Platforms

Before examining the current state-of-the-art, it is essential to establish a clear methodology for evaluating allocation algorithms in cloud manufacturing platforms. Evaluation poses a significant challenge in the design of mechanisms for cloud manufacturing platforms, as many distribution methods are tailored to the unique characteristics of their target markets. These methods often rely on specific scenarios and datasets for self-assessment, leading to variability in the evaluation metrics employed [73]. After reviewing and analyzing the relevant literature, evaluation can be broadly classified into three main categories: the feasibility, the allocation efficiency, and the computation time.

4.1. Feasibility

Cloud manufacturing platforms are utilized across diverse applications, including marine, automotive, and additive manufacturing markets. Since some mechanism designs are tailored to specific manufacturing areas, feasibility becomes a fundamental criterion for evaluating these designs. To verify feasibility, mechanism designers often conduct case studies using real-world datasets or invite manufacturers to participate in simulations [67]. Feasibility verification not only serves as a basic requirement but also reflects the extensibility of a mechanism. Mechanisms with strong extensibility are more adaptable and capable of being applied to a broader range of scenarios [74].

4.2. Allocation Efficiency

Broadly speaking, allocation efficiency encompasses a set of indicators that evaluate the impact of allocation outcomes on the overall system.

1. Social welfare: In economics and game theory, social welfare represents the overall benefit to the system [75]. In the context of the CMfg, it is generally defined as the total sum of benefits accrued by both customers and manufacturers. Social welfare is a key factor in evaluating distribution schemes, which reflects the overall profit generated by the system as a whole, serving as a crucial metric for assessing the effectiveness of the allocation.
2. Mutual satisfaction: Manufacturers' and customers' satisfaction, as direct participants in the platform, serves as a critical evaluation parameter for mechanism design. Satisfaction scores for both parties can be measured by conducting simulations that involve real companies, providing practical insights into the effectiveness of the platform [19]. Building on the evaluation of manufacturer and customer satisfaction, some studies have introduced the difference in satisfaction between the two parties as an additional assessment indicator. A larger satisfaction gap suggests a greater imbalance in the mechanism, highlighting potential areas for improvement in achieving equitable outcomes [76].
3. Fairness: In bilateral platforms, the monopolistic competitiveness of large companies remains a significant challenge. Ensuring fairness in mechanism design is essential to prevent SMEs from being placed at a significant disadvantage in the competitive landscape [70].
4. Sensitivity: Typically evaluated in bilateral matching, where the objective is to generate stable pairs, sensitivity measures the ability of a matching mechanism to consistently produce stable matches under varying environmental parameters.

4.3. Computation Time

Mathematical optimization plays a central role in CMfg resource allocation. Unilateral matching is inherently a solution to a mathematical model, while preference matching in bilateral settings and winner confirmation in auctions are also frequently addressed through optimization techniques. The solution time, which directly impacts how long customers wait for each allocation, serves as a critical metric for evaluating the operational efficiency of the mechanism [17].

5. Resource Allocation in CMfg: State-of-the-art

This section delves into the various modeling techniques and algorithms used in public cloud manufacturing platforms to address resource matching and allocation challenges following the classification aforementioned. By examining these methods, insights can be gained into how they effectively balance the competing interests of resource demanders and providers, improving the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of the manufacturing process.

5.1. One-sided Matching Modeling

In the earlier discussion within Section 3.1 on the matching-based approach, it was noted that the platform has access to information from both sides: the customer's order details and the manufacturer's capacity information. The key distinction between the one-sided and two-sided approaches lies in whether the platform's decisions consider the preferences and interests of only one party or both parties.

In a one-sided matching approach, only the interests of one party are considered, allowing the matching problem to be framed as an optimization problem. A typical optimization problem is shown below [77]:

$$\text{Maximize/Minimize: } f(x) = f(x_1, x_2) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } x_1 \in U_1 \quad (2)$$

$$x_2 \in U_2 \quad (3)$$

where the $f(x)$ is the objective function, x_1 and x_2 are decision variables, and U_1 and U_2 are feasible sets for x_1 and x_2 , respectively. In this optimization problem, the objective function $f(x)$ in Eq(1) reflects the concern for unilateral interest, which can be the makespan of the project or the overall cost [78].

The single-objective optimization problem above will evolve into a multi-objective optimization problem when there are multiple objectives to optimize [79]:

$$\text{Maximize/Minimize: } X_o = f_1(x_1, x_2) + f_2(x_1, x_2) + \dots + f_n(x_1, x_2) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } x_1 \in U_1 \quad (5)$$

$$x_2 \in U_2 \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of objective functions.

Cheng et al. [80] defines utility functions for manufacturer-centered matching in terms of cost, risk, and energy consumption. However, most one-sided matching designs are customer-centered. In such approaches, Quality of Service (QoS) is typically used as the criterion to measure the provider's services within a service-oriented architecture [81], and it is the most commonly selected metric for customer-centered matching in cloud manufacturing [82]. Que et al. [83] presents a common categorization of QoS criteria, including lead time, reliability, cost, and capacity. Huang et al. [84] categorizes cloud manufacturing resources into software and hardware, proposing several corresponding QoS metrics such as user evaluation, hardware energy consumption, and hardware rental fees. Hayyolalam et al. [85] extends these with additional indicators, including energy consumption, scalability, system robustness, and reputation.

After identifying user benefits and QoS as optimization objectives, the algorithm for solving the one-sided matching problem is then discussed.

5.1.1. Exact Optimization for One-sided Matching

An exact algorithm provides a method that leads to an explicit solution, and Lagrangian Coordination (LC) is a commonly used exact algorithm in multi-agent systems that maintain autonomy [86]. Zhang et al. [87] applied the LC method to the cloud manufacturing service selection problem, developing an Augmented Lagrangian Coordination (ALC) method that decomposes the system's resource allocation problem into three sub-problems. Based on this work, they further introduced new coordination elements to solve the task allocation problem under limited production capacities [88] and energy consumption-centered scenarios [89]. Zhang et al. evaluated their proposed ALC algorithm using real-world data and compared its performance with other optimization algorithms. The ALC algorithm achieved the same level of social welfare as the centralized approach but required a longer computation time compared to the centralized GA. However, it outperformed the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm in decentralized scenarios, demonstrating its effectiveness in such contexts.

The use of exact algorithms exemplified by LC can lead to near-optimal allocation schemes, but there are some shortcomings. Exact algorithms tend to be more computationally intensive than non-exact algorithms [90], such as heuristics. Also in practical applications of cloud manufacturing platforms, the parameters of manufacturing tasks and manufacturing services are huge [40] [91], and the solution speed of exact algorithms may not be

able to meet the practical needs [92]. Finally, exact algorithms require accurate modeling of scenarios, which is not flexible enough in dynamic markets with customized demands [93] [94] and rescheduling for unexpected situations [95].

5.1.2. Heuristic Method for One-sided Matching

Heuristic method is an algorithm that empirically designs a search strategy for a solution, which does not guarantee that an optimal solution can be obtained, but the solution is faster than an exact method [96].

The heuristic algorithms for One-sided Matching are basically based on Genetic Algorithm (GA), Particle Swarm Algorithm (PSA) and Bee Colony Algorithm (BCA) [17]. In addition to these methods, Tong et al. [97] designed a parallel search method based on the Gray Wolf algorithm (GWO) to improve its disadvantage of being difficult to find local optimal solutions, and applied this method to single-objective and multi-objective matching. Results showed that the proposed algorithm outperforms Improved Artificial Bee Colony (IABC) [98], Improved Gray Wolf Algorithm (IGWO) [99], and Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm Based on Decomposition (MOEA) [100] in scenario coverage and achieves faster computational speed in most cases. Wang et al. [101] designed a method based on digital twins by assigning real-time information about a manufacturer's machine.

For models with multiple QoS metrics as objective functions, the Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) [102] is among the most widely used approaches. Numerous studies have applied and enhanced this algorithm to address various challenges. Jiang et al. [103] developed a mathematical model for multi-objective matching in the disassembly problem and designed the corresponding NSCA-II operators to improve this algorithm. Zheng et al. [104] used an array of integers as an operator for NSCA-II and used this approach to solve the energy perception problem.

5.1.3. Learning-based Method

In recent years, research on the use of Reinforcement Learning (RL) in solving optimization problems has attracted much attention. RL and its variants have advantages in terms of solution speed and performance in facing complex scenarios in the allocation problem of CMfg.

In their work, Pahwa et al. [105] applied The Deep Q-Network (DQN) algorithm to CMfg distribution, where suppliers are considered as agents, who act in the environment (MaaS marketplace). Ping et al. [106] proposed

a DQN and Double DQN algorithms for supporting edge-side manufacturers in cloud-edge collaboration manufacturing. Results showed that the proposed DRL method outperforms the other seven baseline algorithms across all tests and eight QoS metrics. Wang et al. [107] combines the attention mechanism and reinforcement learning to propose a new policy model in cloud manufacturing allocation. In another work [108], they also proposed a multi-agent RL method where each task to be assigned is considered as an agent to be trained. The experimental results show that the proposed algorithm ranks second to GA in QoS metric evaluation. However, while GA requires thousands of seconds to compute results, the proposed method delivers outcomes in just a few seconds, making it one of the most advanced approaches for one-sided matching.

One-sided Matching reduces computational complexity and provides platforms with the ability to find solutions quickly, but ignoring one side's interests and preferences may lead to the loss of platform users. Although one-sided matching is heavily used in industry, this unbalanced matching does not guarantee user loyalty and stability of the manufacturing system in the long run. The table 1 summarizes the one-sided matching methods.

Table 1: Summary of One-sided Matching Methods

Class	Method	Pros	Cons	References
Exact Methods	Lagrangian coordination	Guaranteed optimal solution	High computation time for large-scale problems	Zhang et al. 2017 [109], Zhang et al. 2018 [87], Zhang et al. 2019 [88], Zhang et al. 2021 [89]
Heuristic Methods	Genetic Algorithm	Can handle complex, large-scale problems	No guarantee of optimal solution	Jiang et al. 2016 [103], Jin et al. 2017 [110], Lin et al. 2017 [111], Yin et al. 2024 [112]
	Bee Colony Algorithm	Highly adaptable to dynamic environments	May require a large number of iterations to converge	Zhou et al. 2017 [113], Zhou et al. 2017 [114], Xu et al. 2017 [115]
	Particle Swarm Algorithm	Fast convergence, adaptable	May not find global optima	Jian et al. 2014 [116], Wang et al. 2014 [117], Du et al. 2019 [118]
	NSCA-II	Efficient for multi-objective optimization problems	May struggle with maintaining diversity	Deb et al. 2002 [102], Jiang et al. 2016 [103], Zheng et al. 2017 [104]
Learning-based Methods	Reinforcement Learning	Fast and flexible response	Difficult to train	Mnih et al. 2015 [105], Wang et al. 2022 [107], Wang et al. 2022 [108], Ping et al. 2023 [106]

5.2. Two-sided Matching

Two-sided matching problem was first proposed by Gale and Shapley [119] for matching between schools and academics in college admissions and for one-to-one marriage matching. Subsequently, matching theory has been widely applied in many fields as one of the important methods of mechanism design, including kidney exchange market [120] and supply chain networks [121].

In two-sided matching, to ensure that the interests of each agent are taken care of, the platform needs to collect preference from both sides. Two-sided matching can be considered as preference-based matching. Building on the definition of the resource allocation problem in the second section, the two-sided matching method is further defined here.

There are two sets:

- Manufacturing Tasks Set: $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{|T|}\}$
- Resources Providers Set: $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{|P|}\}$

Each resources provider $p \in P$ can accept a limited number of tasks. The capacity of provider p is denoted by q_p meaning it can be matched with up to q_p tasks.

Denote the Matching as a mapping [122]:

$$\mu : T \cup P \longrightarrow 2^{T \cup P} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \mu(p) \subseteq T, |\mu(p)| \leq q_p, \forall p \in P \quad (8)$$

$$\mu(t) \subseteq P, |\mu(t)| \leq 1, \forall t \in T \quad (9)$$

$$\mu(p) = \{t\} \Leftrightarrow t \in \mu(p) \quad (10)$$

where Equation (7) represents the mapping, $T \cup P$ indicates the union of two sets and $2^{T \cup P}$ represents all possible subsets of $T \cup P$, (8) indicates that each resource provider cannot accept more tasks than its capacity, (9) indicates that each manufacturing task can be assigned to only one manufacturer, and (10) indicates that the matching is established implying that a manufacturing task s is assigned to a manufacturer p at the same time as a manufacturer p is assigned a task s .

For each manufacturing task, the demander provides a sorted list of preferences \succ_t . For example, $p_1 \succ_t p_2$ means the manufacturer prefers the provider p_1 over p_2 for task t . Similarly, manufacturers have preferences

for tasks: \succ_p . Note that in this paper, preferences are assumed to be strict: \succ rather than non-strict: \succeq . Non-strict preferences imply “better or the be equal to”.

In the two-sided matching, Stable matching is the primary objective. A match μ is stable when it is not blocked by other pairs. In other words, it is that no better match can be found for any other, which means that no better match can be found for any participant.

The following will begin by explaining how to gather preference information, and then proceed to describe how to make matching choices based on that information.

5.2.1. Probability Preference-Based Matching

The simplest method of generating preference information is subjective ranking by customers and manufacturers based directly on each other’s information [123]. However, due to the complexity of manufacturing scenarios, it is difficult to accurately rank preferences based on subjective conscious assessment alone [124].

Figure 6: Utility Function Based Matching (adapted from [125])

Thekinen et al. [125] first applied matching theory to cloud manufacturing and proposed a probability functions and utility functions combination method to represent agents’ preferences. The procedure is showed in Figure 6, s represents manufacturing resources seekers (customers), p represents manufacturing resources providers providers (manufacturers), R indicates rankings, μ represents the matching. The customer and the manufacturer should each provide their own attributes; the customer’s attributes include the requirements of the order, such as lead time or accuracy requirements

and the manufacturer's attribute list should contain a description of its production capabilities. Then, a single-attribute utility function [126] is used to assess customers' and manufacturers' preferences for an attribute of the other. Single utility functions are combined to form the multi-utility function for every customer or manufacturer. The multi-attribute utility function is further combined with the probability function for each attribute value to form a final expected utility function. This generates an probability-utility function, and the expected utility is sorted by value to form a preference list.

Delaram et al. [67] further proposed a single-attribute probability function characterized by a Gaussian distribution for those with attribute tolerance coefficients. All of the aforementioned probability preference-based matching methods have demonstrated their feasibility in tests. Moreover, testing different acceptance algorithms has revealed that the optimal acceptance algorithm varies based on supply and demand conditions and the degree of market monopoly.

5.2.2. Fuzzy Preference-Based Matching

Hesitation and ambiguity are challenges when dealing with preference information, and participants tend to show uncertainty about their preference for an attribute[127]. The use of hesitant fuzzy sets better addresses the complexity of manufacturing system attributes and the uncertainty of user decision-making in reality than a fully quantitative approach [128]. In this

Figure 7: Procedure of IF-VIKOR (adapted from [129])

work, Li et al. [52] generates preference information using dual hesitant fuzzy sets for modeling subjective evaluations, a process as visually outlined in Figure 8, which is regarded as one of the best practices in fuzzy preference-based matching. The process is divided into three phases: the first phase generates a normalized preference information matrix based on the preferences of both parties; the second phase converts this matrix into a satisfaction matrix and formulates a mathematical model for multi-objective optimization; and the third phase focuses on solving the model. The algorithm achieves matching efficiency approximately three times higher than several previous fuzzy preference matching methods. Zheng et al. [130] employs interval-valued hesitant

fuzzy linguistic sets (IVHFLSs) for all linguistic preference information that is difficult to quantify to characterize the degree of preference, the result showed that the method is slightly more efficient than the algorithm [52] mentioned before. Delaram et al. [38] designed a method that combines the VIKOR [129] method and fuzzy sets to build preference information, in order to avoid the effects of system complexity, the procedure is illustrated in Figure 7. Wu et al. [131] employs triangular fuzzy numbers to transform uncertainty information into preferences. Xian et al. [132] proposed a comprehensive satisfaction calculation and interval satisfaction matrix to represent preference information based on hesitant fuzzy sets. There is also some work that attempts

Figure 8: Generate Preference Information by Dual Hesitant Fuzzy Set (adapted from [52])

to model uncertain preferences based on information from multiple dimensions. Zhang et al. [133] employs uncertain linguistic variables, preference

sequences, and complementarity matrices to characterize multidimensional preferences. In another work [134], Zhang and Yang proposed a method for constructing preference information through three different types of uncertainty information. His series of work emphasizes stability (low sensitivity) and the public accessibility of the mechanism, outperforming other designs in these aspects.

5.2.3. Hybrid Preference-Based Matching

Some research target to combine the strengths of the probability and fuzzy theory together. Hu et al. [135] combined fuzzy integrated assessment and hierarchical analysis to produce preference information using a five-level scoring and weighting model; the feasibility of the method is verified on 30 instances. Liu et al. [136] further combined prospect theory and gray correlation analysis calculations to express preferences based on the cloud model. Tong et al. [74] introduced the cloud model [137] to define how preferences can be obtained from fuzzy expressions and randomness transformations, the proposed method outperforms the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm and NSGA-II in solution speed.

5.2.4. Historical information for Preference

For platforms that have already accumulated some transaction data, using historical data to generate preferences is a faster method. Tong et al. [138] proposed sequential preferences for obtaining preferences based on historical information. Wang et al. [139] proposed a method of using hierarchical analysis to obtain preferences through historical information. Li et al. [140] uses hierarchical analysis to transform the historical information in the platform into a preference evaluation. Huang et al. [141] presented a method for generating preferences from historical information using a convolutional neural network. This model, compared with several other machine learning methods [142] [143] [144] [145] [146], demonstrates superior performance in matching recommendation effectiveness and computational efficiency.

5.2.5. Selection Method

After getting the preference information, the platform needs to apply certain selection methods to complete the matching. Gale and Shapley proposed the Delayed Acceptance (DA) algorithm [119] when they proposed bilateral matching in the marriage market. Afterwards, DA was applied as one of the

mainstream algorithms for bilateral matching in problems such as job market matching [147], college admissions [148], and so on.

The DA algorithm is an iterative process for generating stable matching. Among participants, one side is considered as the proposing side, and the receiver side decides whether to accept or reject it [149]. The proposing side proposes their highest-ranked choice, and the receiver side tentatively accepts the best proposal while rejecting others. Rejected proposers then propose their next preference in subsequent rounds. This continues until no more proposals are made, resulting in stable matches where no pair prefers each other over their current match [147].

Thekinen et al. [125] compared DA with Top Trading Cycle (TTC) [150], Munkres [151], and first-come-first-service (FCFS) [152] algorithms in the cloud manufacturing scenario, and the results show that DA works best in matching fully decentralized manufacturing resources among these four algorithms.

Delaram et al. [67] conducted experiments with two different scenarios, where either customers or manufacturers acted as the proposing side. The results showed that when the capacity of the participating manufacturers is sufficient to cover the order, consumers achieve better matching results as the proposing side. However, when the manufacturers' capacity is smaller than required, the manufacturer should act as the proposing side in the Deferred Acceptance (DA) algorithm. This experimental insight aligns with market intuition: when platforms are in equilibrium or oversupplied, allowing the dominant party (customers) to choose first helps stabilize the system; conversely, allowing manufacturers to choose first in undersupplied scenarios adheres to market dynamics.

Yang et al. [49] presented a methodology for changing the proposed side in response to changes in capacity. Pahwa et al. [153] proposed formulas for maximizing social welfare (total profit of system) and approximate stability in matching and uses them in the proposal acceptance determination formula in DA. Tong et al. [138] developed a bi-objective optimization model with the satisfaction of both parties and applied a genetic algorithm to solve it. Li [52] established a multi-objective optimization model with the objectives of maximizing the satisfaction of both parties and minimizing the degree of discrepancy, and then further transformed the multi-objective model into a single-objective model for solving. Huo et al. [154] selected time, quality, cost and expectation as the objectives to construct the model and then applied Evolutionary Game Algorithm (EGA) to solve it, which achieves bet-

ter performance than the Canonical Genetic Algorithm (CGA), Local Search Genetic Algorithm (LsGA), and Fuzzy Adaptive Genetic Algorithm (FaGA).

Mathematical models (MM), especially multi-objective models, are also one of the common methods for matching. For example, Li et al. [52] used multi-objective optimization to determine matching after transforming uncertain preference information into an evaluation matrix. Zheng et al. [130] established a mathematical model with the objectives of ensuring satisfaction and pairwise stability, and they applied an adaptive genetic algorithm to solve the problem.

Figure 9: Reducing matching size through clustering [74]

For the large-scale matching problem, Tong et al. [74] proposed a method based on density-based clustering method (DBCM) [155] for clustering non-convex preference information, splitting the large-scale problem into small-scale problems and then completing the matching, the flowchart is presented in Fig 9, participants from two sides were clustered and then matching happened for every small cluster.

Table 2: Summary Table for Two-sided Matching

Reference	Preference				Selection Algorithm		
	Probability	Fuzzy Theory	Hybrid	Historical Data	DA	MM	Other
Huo et al. 2021 [154]	✓					✓	
Li et al. 2020 [127]		✓				✓	
Wu et al. 2016 [131]		✓					✓
Tong et al. 2020 [76]		✓				✓	
Delaram et al. 2021 [156]		✓			✓		
Mubarok et al. 2018 [157]	✓					✓	
Zhang and Yang 2022 [134]	✓					✓	
Liu et al. 2021 [136]			✓			✓	
Tong et al. 2022 [74]			✓			✓	
Hu et al. 2021 [135]			✓				✓
Zheng et al. 2021 [130]	✓					✓	
Delaram et al. 2023 [38]		✓			✓		
Tong et al. 2020 [138]				✓		✓	
Luo et al. 2020 [158]	✓					✓	
Li et al. 2019 [52]		✓				✓	
Delaram et al. 2021 [67]	✓				✓		
Yang et al. 2021 [49]	✓					✓	✓
Feng et al. 2017 [159]		✓					✓
Thekinen et al. 2017 [125]	✓				✓		
Pahwa et al. 2020 [153]	✓					✓	
Huang et al. 2024 [141]				✓			✓

5.2.6. Summary for Two-sided Matching

Two-sided matching algorithms aim to satisfy the preferences of both parties and form stable matches, which in the long run increases the retention of users on both sides of the fence while adding robustness to the manufacturing system. Table 2 demonstrates a summary of past studies of past two-sided matching. Preference acquisition methods based on probability and fuzzy theory have attracted significant attention, with scholars developing efficient approaches for generating preference lists. In contrast, research on selective recommendation and preference prediction using historical data remains scarce, primarily due to the challenges associated with data collection. Pairing through mathematical models effectively captures requirements, but maintaining solution efficiency as problem size increases remains a significant challenge. Further research is needed to enhance solution performance.

5.3. Auction-based Method

Auctions are one of the most common methods of resource allocation [160], and auction theory has been applied in a number of areas: spectrum allocation [161], electricity markets [162], e-commerce online auction [163], and so on. For the manufacturing resource allocation of public cloud manufacturing

platforms, auction is another decentralized allocation method that balances the interests of both sides [164] in addition to the matching method.

Auction-based approaches are suitable for dynamic, competitive scenarios where bidders express their preferences by submitting bids, and the maximization of the system's benefits is later coordinated through the platform's collection of bids. In manufacturing markets, there are typically four steps in the design of an auction mechanism:

1. Auction Frameworks Selection. Auctions are an important topic in economics, and there have been many studies in the literature and practical applications of specific auction models: First-Price Auction [165], Second-Price Auction (Vickrey Auction) [166], Reverse Auction [167], Combinatorial Auctions [168], Iterative Auction, and so on [169]. How to find the best practices in cloud manufacturing scenarios is one of the major concerns.
2. Objective Determination. This step defines the objective of the auction, which is typically set to maximize social welfare [170]. In other words, the aim is to optimize the overall benefit of the system.
3. Bidding Design. The platform needs to specify the method by which participants should present their bids, either numerically (e.g., quotes) or as equations (e.g., utility functions) [171].
4. Winner Determination. The platform needs to allocate orders based on bids, and the design of the determination method includes whether the determination is based on one or multiple targets and on which criteria [172]. Another important task is how to increase the speed of determination.

The following sections will discuss auction design in their respective scenarios, categorized from consumers-as-bidders and manufacturers-as-bidders.

5.3.1. Demander-as-bidders Auctions

Demander-as-bidders often occur in additive manufacturing markets, where customers bid for the capacity of a manufacturer. In the additive manufacturing market, 3D printers serve as a key manufacturing resource [173]. Smaller companies, with fewer machines available, often face disadvantages in direct competition, while customers prioritize efficient and rapid distribution [174]. Given these dynamics, research on allocation schemes for additive manufacturing cloud platforms emphasizes two main objectives: fairness, to encour-

age competition among small and medium-sized companies, and efficiency, to ensure the prompt resolution of the winner determination problem.

To ensure fairness in distribution, Pahwa et al. [19] applied the Reverse Auction model [175] to the additive manufacturing market. In this approach, resource seekers submit bids, and the platform facilitates matching while promoting fair competition by reducing direct competition between large companies and small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) among resource providers. Additionally, Pahwa et al. introduced bid-value recommendation and randomizer modules to the traditional Reverse Auction process [175]. These enhancements aim to encourage participants to bid at reasonable prices while preventing malicious underbidding by large suppliers. The framework is illustrated in Fig. 10. The proposed design, tested in a comparative experiment against a competitive platform, outperformed its competitor in both satisfaction and fairness metrics.

Figure 10: Reverse auction with randomizer [19]

For the price model in the reverse auction, Lu et al. [176] investigated the pricing problem in auctions, proposing a pricing model that integrates game, market information, price sensitivity and demand in reverse auctions.

In another work [177], Mashhadi et al. ensures fairness through randomness by developing a dynamic stochastic auction mechanism designed to address scenarios with uncertain target demand. The architecture of this mechanism is presented in Fig 11, where resource buyers submit their bids and manufacturers upload their capacity to AM cloud. To efficiently solve the winner determination problem, he further proposed a deep learning model to solve the winner determination problem [178].

For the large scale winner determination problem, Liu et al. [179] pro-

Figure 11: Architecture of Consumers-as-bidders Auctions.

posed a multi-stage iterative auction, in order to avoid the difficulty of solving the winner determination problem when there are too many auction tasks; at the same time, he developed an algorithm based on simulated annealing algorithm to solve the winner determination, which greatly improves the determination speed. In simulation experiments, this method was compared with the decentralized negotiation mechanism inspired by simulated annealing (NMSA) and the centralized methods GA and PSO. The results demonstrate that, in large-scale problems, the proposed method surpasses the social welfare achieved by the state-of-the-art decentralized method (NMSA) and matches the performance of centralized methods.

5.3.2. Provider-as-bidders Auctions

Provider-as-bidder auctions are suitable for scenarios where large orders are allocated. In this auction model, determining the allocation that ensures

the efficient completion of the project is of paramount importance.

Figure 12: Framework of Second-price Reverse Combinatorial Auction [180]

Figure 13: Example of the bundling process [180]

Second-price auctions are a commonly used model in this scenario, where the winner pays the second-highest bid instead of their own. This approach is designed to encourage participants to submit honest and competitive offers [181].

Based on the second-price auction, Liu et al. [70] proposed a continuous bidding model, where participants will bid on each manufacturing task knowing that all tasks have a match. The proposed auction generates an allocation scheme that outperforms the GA and Earliest Due Date (EDD) algorithms in simulation experiments and demonstrates feasibility with real datasets. Zehetner et al. [180] combines second-price auctions, reverse auctions, and combinatorial auctions to propose a framework, illustrated in Fig 12, where manufacturing tasks are bundled first, showed in the Fig13, then bids are

invited and only then a second price is paid as the winner. The method has been tested on hundreds of instances, outperforming centralized methods (GA and its variants) in computational efficiency and cost control. Yu et al. [182] models the dynamic process in auctions as a Markov decision model while using long short-term memory (LSTM) to predict future demand, combined with deep reinforcement learning to optimize the strategy. In comparative experiments with Full Information Approach (FI), Static Information Dynamic Programming Approach (SDP), and Bayesian Information Updating Dynamic Programming Approach (BDP), the proposed method demonstrates superior performance across all scenarios.

5.3.3. Double Auctions

The Double Auction mechanism is designed to balance the interests of both manufacturers and customers [183]. Customers' bids reflect their willingness to pay and are ranked in ascending order, while manufacturers' bids represent their offers for orders and are ranked in descending order. In recent years, double auctions have gained significant attention in CMfg markets, with numerous studies integrating them with combinatorial auctions to enhance allocation efficiency.

Liu et al. [72] was the first to implement a double auction mechanism in cloud manufacturing (CMfg), introducing an iterative double auction that allocates orders by thoroughly considering factors such as task priority, type, and transportation, thereby achieving incentive compatibility. Building upon this, Antón et al. [184] further addresses the supply/demand imbalance in the additive manufacturing market by proposing an iterative combinatorial double auction that helps manufacturers accept multiple parts from the same build area. Kang et al. [185] presented a double auction for various homogeneous items and analyzed the market clearing price to balance supply and demand.

Table 3: Summary Table for Auction-based Method

Type	Reference	Characteristic
Manufacturers-as-bidders	Liu et al. 2019 [70]	Second-price auctions; consecutive auctions; multiple objective criteria; focus on fairness
	Zehetner et al. 2024 [180]	Second-price Reverse Auction
	Sparr et al. 2021 [186]	Cyclic Bidding Until Stop Conditions Met
	Yu et al. 2024 [182]	Markov chain modeling; AI model prediction
Consumers-as-bidders	Mashhadi et al. 2019 [177]	Uncertain Requirements; Randomized Multi-item Auctions
	Mashhadi et al. 2020 [178]	Deep Learning Solving Winner Determination Problem
	Lu et al. 2020 [176]	Reverse Auctions; Price Sensitivity-based Modeling
	Liu et al. 2022 [179]	Termination conditions for mixed auctions
Double Auction	Antón et al. 2024 [184]	Iterative Combinatorial Double Auction
	Liu et al. 2019 [72]	Iterative Double Auction with Logistics Options
	Kang et al. 2020 [185]	Multi-unit Double Auction; Market-clearing Price Model
	Zhang et al. 2023 [187]	Double Auction in Budget Limited Condition

5.3.4. Summary for Auction-based Methods

Auction-based methods, summarized in table 3, which are mostly used in the competitive market, for example additive manufacturing, are very efficient in dynamic and competitive environments, but there may be fairness issues for participants with enough capital to potentially choose to compete badly by compressing costs. Auctions inherently function as mechanisms of competitive financial incentives, making it challenging to prevent large firms from gaining an overwhelming advantage.

6. Discussion and Future Research

The one-sided matching, two-sided matching, and auction-based approaches have gained significant attention in recent years as key frameworks for addressing the resource allocation problem in public cloud manufacturing platforms.

Figure 14: Comparison of cloud manufacturing allocation mechanisms.

Fig 14 illustrates a comparison of the architecture and flow of one-sided matching, two-sided matching, and three auction-based methods. Of these, the one-sided matching algorithm has garnered the most attention and is the most widely adopted in industry. Its primary advantage lies in its ability to generate allocation schemes quickly by focusing on the customer's needs, which helps attract and retain customers. However, this customer-centric

approach can have negative long-term effects on market structure. From the platform's perspective, manufacturers may choose to leave if their interests are not adequately safeguarded. Additionally, from a social and economic standpoint, such a model may foster unhealthy competition among manufacturers, destabilizing the broader manufacturing system. As a result, there is a growing need for research into matching methods that account for the interests of both parties.

Two-sided matching and auction-based methods, both of which consider the interests of both parties, have distinct characteristics. Auction-based methods is primarily a price-based allocation method, while two-sided matching rely on preference-based allocation. Two-sided matching emphasizes fairness and stability, with stability often being the top priority. This approach is particularly suited to markets where preferences remain relatively stable over time and where long-term, consistent cooperation between customers and manufacturers is expected.

In contrast, the auction-based approach focuses on efficiency. Resources are allocated to the participant with the highest bid, ensuring that allocation is both efficient and responsive to market demand. This method is better suited to dynamic environments, where supply and demand fluctuate more frequently. Additionally, it offers high scalability, making it capable of managing a large number of participants.

There remains a disconnect between algorithmic research and its practical implementation in industry, primarily due to challenges in efficiency and risk. Algorithms like bilateral matching and auctions require significant time to execute, while industrial allocation methods demand instant quoting. Additionally, the risk of distributing orders across multiple manufacturers limits the usability of many algorithms.

Addressing the challenges faced by manufacturing SMEs in Europe, we propose that future manufacturing paradigms, building on existing cloud manufacturing platforms, should integrate manufacturers and customers more intelligently using IoT, AI, and blockchain technologies. AI can enhance allocation efficiency; reinforcement and deep learning can enable pre-allocation, while large language models can assist in capturing user preferences. IoT and blockchain, on the other hand, can ensure product quality in collaborative production by establishing transparent and traceable supply chain quality management. Future resource allocation solutions will have to work closely with these techniques to ensure that more SMEs can benefit from the platform.

Building on this new concept of platformization, hybrid solutions that address bilateral interests warrant further investigation. Auction-based methods are particularly effective for scenarios involving multiple manufacturers and, given the predominance of SMEs, should serve as the primary approach. Simultaneously, matching methods can play a significant role in pre-allocations, and their integration with auction mechanisms has the potential to significantly enhance system efficiency.

For future research, several noteworthy directions should be considered:

- **Dynamic Two-Sided Matching with Real-Time Adaptation Powered by AI:** A key challenge in two-sided matching is the extended processing time when preferences change frequently. Advanced AI techniques, such as deep learning, can be utilized to predict future preferences based on historical data and order information. Additionally, large language models could be employed to extract unstructured preferences for real-time dynamic processing.
- **Fairness and Diversity:** To improve system stability and promote fairness, platforms should consider the needs of SMEs that may not be financially advantaged and are more vulnerable to competitive pressures. Incorporating these factors into the mechanism design could help prevent unfair disadvantages and support the long-term sustainability of the system.
- **Incorporating Machine Learning into Auction Design:** Machine learning methods introduce a data-driven approach to parameterization in auction design. While traditional auctions are typically tailored to specific scenarios or market segments, the integration of machine learning enhances the flexibility of auction mechanisms, enabling their application in non-manufacturing markets as well.
- **IoT-Powered Distribution:** Resource allocation depends heavily on information from both resource demanders and providers. However, data collection and processing can be time-consuming, and ensuring the accuracy of the information remains a challenge. With advancements in information technology, particularly the Internet of Things (IoT), one key future direction is to accelerate edge-side computation and enhance coordination with the platform through automation technologies.

7. Conclusion

This paper provides a systematic analysis of several approaches and frameworks for manufacturing resource allocation in the Public Cloud Manufacturing platform. It analyzes its strengths and weaknesses, highlights current gaps, and outlines future challenges. The Public Cloud Manufacturing platform plays a crucial role in integrating manufacturing resources, enabling SMEs to expand their customer base, and enhancing the overall robustness of manufacturing ecosystems.

Current resource allocation methods can be categorized into three types: One-sided Matching, Two-sided Matching, and Auction-based Method. One-sided Matching considers only the consumers' interests and is usually modeled as a multi-objective optimization problem with QoS as the objective; Two-sided Matching focuses on how to generate stable manufacturer-customer pairings, and a series of generative preference ranking methods using probability theory and fuzzy set theory have been proposed in previous studies, along with the use of historical data for recommendation and pre-matching; and Auction-based Method efficiently accomplish resource allocation, bidder design, pricing models and various auction methods have been explored by scholars, with reverse auction being the most applied solution.

The number of one-sided matching studies accounts for around 70% of literature found in this field, significantly outnumbering the other two approaches which are able to satisfy the interests of both sides and maintain the robustness and stability of the whole manufacturing system. Advances in information technology, such as large language models and digital twins, have the potential to greatly improve the efficiency of two-sided matching. However, research in this area remains limited. Similarly, for auction-based methods, there is a lack of studies on allocating large-scale manufacturing orders, and more attention is needed on bid setting and game strategies.

A new turning point in manufacturing has arrived, and a bilateral manufacturing platform that harmonizes SMEs while connecting consumers is imminent. Previous research on Public Cloud Manufacturing platforms has provided a good foundation for a new manufacturing paradigm, but there are still gaps and challenges on the way to a new generation of manufacturing systems, and this paper aims to review the proposed research and point the way to a new manufacturing paradigm for the future.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jinhan Gao: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draf. **Ricardo Knoblauch:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Mohamed El Mansori:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the language and readability of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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